

HIERARCHICAL LIGHTWEIGHT COMPOSITES: GF FABRICS EMBEDDED IN MICROCELLULAR NANOCOMPOSITE PEN

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1 Introduction

It is well established that composites are used because of their high specific quasi-static properties (for example tensile and flexural moduli, and strengths) [1] but their impact resistance is usually poor, and tougheners are needed to reduce this issue in thermosets matrices. Improvements can be obtained through the use of thermoplastic matrices, but crystallization could be an important issue when a semicrystalline polymer is used to increase the elastic modulus or have solvent resistance of the matrix. In this case very careful processing conditions must be used for evenly crystallize the thermoplastic matrix and avoiding the induction of residual internal stresses.

Until now composites have been designed by strictly limiting the voids content in the matrix, because they are considered defective points that can originate cracks and lead to the failure of the laminate. Sandwich structures are the only composites which allow pores, and only outside the fiber reinforced layers. The sandwich approach is used to obtain very stiff and light structures, and is characterized by the bonding of a low density core (usually an honeycomb or a foam) to two outer composite skins responsible for the structural performances [2]. Both composites and foamed cores are usually based on thermosets, but also in this composite design thermoplastics could be preferred due to their high toughness, no chemical reactions during fabrication, short manufacturing cycle, possibility of both scraps recovery, in-use repairing and the possibility to thermoforming [3-5]. Conventional sandwich design does not add any contribution to the impact resistance; it is completely devolved to composite skins, which in turn rule the impact resistance and the damage tolerance. Several methods have been tried to improve the core contribution to energy

dissipation, such as stitching [6], textile reinforced folded core [7], embedding of syntactic microspheres [8] or introduction of nanoparticles into the core matrix [9].

In order to improve the impact resistance, a new concept for a lightweight composite structure, inspired to the multiscale lightweight porous structures of natural composites such as wood and bone, is proposed. It is based on high performance thermoplastic matrix in which large amounts of pores are generated between reinforcing fabric layers and within fiber bundles in the composite laminate. In order to enhance the pores morphology and to improve matrix properties, expanded graphite nanofiller has also been embedded [10-12].

2 Experimental

Poly(ethylene 2,6-naphthalate) (PEN) (Teonex TN8065S from Teijin, Japan) was used as thermoplastic matrix ($T_g = 125$ °C, $T_m = 265$ °C). Proprietary grade expanded graphite (EG) particles (platelets mean width smaller than 65 μm , platelets thickness smaller than 1 μm) were supplied by GrafTech International Holdings Inc., and used to prepare PEN nanocomposites.

Nanoparticles were dispersed in the polymer by using a Haake Rheocord (Thermo, Germany) PTW25P twin screw extruder at a screw speed of 40 rpm (5 minutes of residence time). PEN samples reinforced with 0.1, 0.5, 1.0 and 2.5 % by weight of EG were prepared. Foams were obtained by using supercritical carbon dioxide as blowing agent and foamed through the solid state foaming technique.

Glass fiber reinforced composites were prepared by using the film stacking process. Eight layers of glass fiber fabric were stacked between nine layers of polyester films (dimensions: 100x100 mm^2). The glass fiber volume content was kept constant at 30% by volume in all samples.

Glass fiber reinforced foamed composites were prepared through a controlled expansion, in an aluminum mould, of the thermoplastic matrix preliminarily solubilized with a physical blowing agent (carbon dioxide) at 80bar and 50°C by using a high pressure vessel. An hydraulic press (model P300P, from Collin GmbH, Germany) was used to prepare samples for both composite foaming and mechanical characterization.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis on nanofilled matrices and foams was performed on cryogenic fractured surfaces with Quanta 200 FEG from FEI (Eindhoven, The Netherlands). All sample surfaces were coated with gold layer before observations to render conductive the specimen surface.

Thermal properties of nanocomposites were evaluated by using a differential scanning calorimeter (Q1000 DSC from TA Instruments - USA). The crystallization temperatures (T_c) and the relative crystallinity (X_c) were determined from cooling scans between room temperature and 300°C at an cooling rate of 10°C/min. Relative crystallinity values, X_c , were evaluated as the ratio $\Delta H_c/\Delta H_m^0$, where ΔH_m^0 is the crystallization enthalpy of the perfect PEN crystal [13]. Graphite dispersion was also investigated through an XRD analyzer at room temperature by using a Philips X-ray generator and a Philips diffractometer, type PW1710. The X-ray beam was a nickel-filtered $CuK\alpha$ radiation of wavelength 1.54 Å operated with the voltage generator set to 40 kV and at a current of 20 mA. The diffraction intensity data were collected automatically at a scanning rate of 0.6°/min with 0.02°/s steps from 5° to 60°.

Flexural properties were measured by means of a universal testing machine (mod. 4304, SANS – China) on 22x95 mm² samples, cut from solid (span-to-depth ratio higher than 24) and foamed (span-to-depth ratio higher than 13) composites according to ASTM D790-10 standard. Impact tests were performed by using a falling dart impact testing machine (Fractovis Plus, CEAST – Italy). Specimens were tested at three impact energies (8.6 J, 43 J, and 61 J) by keeping constant the mass (6.929 kg) of the indenter equipped with a hemispherical head (diameter equal to 12.7 mm). The sample holder was circular, with the external diameter of 60 mm and the inner one of 30 mm.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Matrix characterization

Expanded graphite increased the crystallization kinetics (higher T_c during cooling from the melt state) of the polymeric matrix with respect to the neat polymer, demonstrating that EG acted as nucleating agents for crystals but it also led to slightly lower maximum crystallinity, due to confinement mechanisms of graphite (Table 1). As a result the presence of EG can be exploited to tailor the crystallization kinetics to the specific needs of further matrix processing in composites.

The characteristic graphite peak is barely visible in nanocomposite XRD patterns (Fig. 1), showing that a good dispersion of nanoparticles was achieved. The absence of significant peaks could be related to both exfoliation of nanoparticles and size reduction due to mechanical stresses applied to the polymer melt by the twin screw extruder.

SAMPLE	Cooling from Melt state		Maximum crystallinity
	X_c [%]	T_c [°C]	X_c [%]
Neat PEN	2.8	187.0	22.94
PEN + 0.1% EG	19.9	205.9	20.52
PEN + 0.5% EG	18.7	205.0	20.11
PEN + 1.0% EG	17.7	201.6	16.72
PEN + 2.5% EG	16.7	205.3	20.49

Table 1. Relative crystallinity of Neat PEN and nanocomposites after cooling from the melt state and maximum crystallinity of matrices

Figure 1. XRD patterns of neat PEN and its expanded graphite nanocomposites

Figure 2. Characterization of nanocomposite matrices in the amorphous and semicrystalline state: A) Flexural Modulus; B) Stress at break; C) Strain at break

Neat and nanocomposite matrices were characterized in both amorphous and crystallized state (Fig. 2). The presence of EG improved the flexural modulus in the amorphous state, but induced a slight reduction in nanocomposite crystallized matrix. This has been addressed to the reduced maximum crystallinity exhibited by nanocomposite samples with respect to crystallized neat samples. On the contrary, benefits on the stress at break and strain at break were obtained in proportion to the EG content with a maximum in the 1.0% sample.

Carbon dioxide uptake into nanocomposite samples has been measured after solubilization in a high pressure vessel and the sorption values are reported in Table 2. The presence of expanded graphite affects the gas uptake significantly with the increase of the EG content, limiting the diffusivity of the gas and the maximum amount of gas uptake (solubility). This will influence the foaming behavior of the nanocomposite matrices.

EG content [%]	Graphite
Neat	5.2
0.1	4.8
0.5	4.1
1.0	4.5
2.5	3.5

Table 2. Blowing agent uptake as function of EG content

3.2 Nanocomposite foams

The foaming process of nanocomposite matrices has been performed at different temperatures (from 200 to 260°C) in order to identify the best processing condition which combines low density and high number of nucleated pores. As evident from Fig. 3, the presence of expanded graphite did not hindered foam density reduction, and for some compositions (0.1% EG) nanocomposite foams showed a density lower than that of the neat polymer. Starting from 240°C the foam density of nanocomposite matrices resulted significantly higher, being affected by the faster crystallization kinetics induced by the presence of EG and the consequent reduction of the maximum expansion ratio.

EG also increased by one order of magnitude the number of nucleated cells with respect to neat PEN, also reducing the average cell size (Fig. 4). It is evident from the SEM micrographs in Fig. 5 the different cellular morphology induced by the presence of EG during the foaming process. This behavior will be still present in foamed composites.

Figure 3. Densities of foams [reported from 12]

Figure 4. Cell densities of PEN nanocomposite foams [reported from 12]

Figure 5. Cell densities of A) neat PEN and B) 0.1% EG nanocomposite foams in the same processing conditions

The nanocomposite with 1.0% of EG exhibited at 220°C the best combination of nucleated cells and foam density and, being the best performing nanocomposite matrix, has been selected as reference composition for the preparation of nanocomposite foamed composites.

For the sake of comparison, a sandwich structure having the same reinforcing content and density of foamed composites has been prepared to show how pores position (within reinforcing layers rather than between solid composite skins) is able to heavily affect the impact behavior of reinforced structures.

3.3 Solid and lightweight composites

Composites prepared by means of the film stacking technique showed a very good fiber impregnation, and extensive optical analysis did not report on void presence into solid matrices. Furthermore, EG particles were detected between reinforcing fibers, showing that they were not sieved by fiber bundles and that they could be exploited to affect the properties of the thermoplastic matrix within fibers (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Details of fiber impregnation in the composite based on 1.0% graphite filled matrix: A) SEM image, B) graphite platelet dispersed between fibers

Physical properties of composite structures are reported in Table 3. Solid composites exhibited a density of around 1.7 g/cm³, while pore containing composites exhibited a density around unity. Voids content in solid composites has been measured by means of water displacement method, and resulted lower than 1%. Voids in lightweight structures were around 40%. The matrix density calculated for foamed composites and sandwich are different, but

the pore content within the two lightweight systems is quite similar. It is worth to note that all samples were prepared by using the same amount of reinforcing glass fiber fabric (30% by volume).

Matrix Type	Neat Comp.	EG Comp.	Neat Foamed	EG Foamed	EG Sandwich
Density (g/cm ³)	1.69	1.67	0.98	0.94	1.03
Matrix Density (g/cm ³)	1.35	1.35	0.67	0.66	0.33
Pores (Vol %)	< 1	< 1	0.42	0.43	0.39

Table 3. Physical data of prepared composite structures

Figure 7. Stiffness and flexural moduli of composite structures

Figure 8. Absolute and specific values of flexural stress

The flexural behavior of all composite structures has been evaluated. Sandwich structure and foamed composites exhibited higher stiffnesses with respect to solid composites, being thicker samples, but the latter showed higher flexural moduli. The performance gap reduces if specific values, after density normalization, are considered (Fig. 7). Flexural stress is, on the contrary, significantly lower in lightweight structures containing pores, also considering specific values (Fig. 8). This result was expected due to the poor shear properties induced by the presence of pores in the structure, and is a common characteristic between sandwich and foamed composites.

Low velocity impact tests have been performed on composite structures at three impact energy values. The lowest value ($E_i = 8.6$ J) has been selected to investigate damages after a not destructive impact, well below the perforation energy of all composite configurations. The second impact energy value ($E_i = 43$ J) is the impact energy at which conventional (solid) composites are perforated. The third impact energy ($E_i = 61$ J) is the impact energy at which foamed composites have been perforated.

Damages after impact in solid composites at $E_i = 8.6$ J showed damaged glass fibers on the back side of the sample (Fig. 9A, and its magnification in 9B) and an evident protrusion (Fig. 9C). In composite samples the low energy impact caused an important indentation under the impact zone, more pronounced in Neat PEN foamed samples.

The absorbed energy as function of the sample density is reported in Fig. 8. Neat foamed composites were able to absorb more than 70% of the impact energy, while EG foamed composite behaved similarly to solid composites (Fig. 10). Foamed composites also showed a reduction of the peak force during low energy impact, as a result of the presence of pores. In particular, Neat foamed samples quite halved the peak force during impact of solid composites (Fig. 11).

At $E_i = 43$ J both neat and EG filled solid composites were perforated (Fig. 9D) while foamed composites were able to bear the impact load without penetration (Fig. 9E – 9G). In this impact conditions the reinforcing fabric was still in very good conditions and apparently was not seriously damaged. The increased energy absorption can be related to dissipative mechanisms involving the

polymeric matrix which are not present in solid composites. In Fig. 12 a magnification of the foamed matrix (after the 8.6 J impact from Fig. 9G) shows that cells between reinforcing fabrics can be compressed, stretched and broken due to the tensional state during dart penetration. Evidence of matrix deformations or breaking are present far from the impacted zone under the impactor head. This means that the presence of pores allows the spreading of the load through larger volumes with respect to solid composites.

Figure 9. Cross sections of impacted samples: A) solid composite, B) solid composite (detail of broken fibers), C) solid composite (back of impacted sample), D) solid composite (back of impacted sample after 43 J impact), E) Neat PEN foamed composite (43 J impact), F) EG filled PEN foamed composite (43 J impact), G) EG filled PEN foamed composite (8.6 J impact), H) EG filled PEN foamed composite (43 J impact)

Foamed composites were penetrated after 56 J and 59 J impact energies for neat PEN matrix and nanocomposite PEN matrix, respectively. These values are up to 43% higher than those exhibited by solid composites. EG nanoparticles allowed an increase of the absorbed energy, in both solid and foamed composites (Table 4).

The peak load was also positively influenced by the presence of EG nanoparticles and by pores (Table 4). In particular, EG Foamed Composite exhibited a peak load strongly improved with respect to EG Composite. This performance can be explained in terms of reinforcing effect of EG on the polymeric matrix and to the finer cellular morphology induced during the foaming process in EG Foamed samples. The EG sandwich sample exhibited an impact resistance comparable to that of the EG solid composite, demonstrating that its energy absorption capability only depended on the reinforcing fabric content into the composite skins. The presence of the

lightweight core was, on the contrary, responsible for the very low peak load during impact, with respect to all other composite configurations.

In Fig. 13 the absolute and specific impact resistance of solid, sandwich and foamed composites are compared. It is evident that the specific impact resistance of foamed composite is more than 2.5 times that of the solid composite.

Figure 10. Absorbed energy as function of composite density

Figure 11. Peak force as function of composite density

The improved impact performance exhibited by foamed composites has been ascribed to complex dissipation mechanisms that involves both the foamed matrix (combination of compression, tensile and shear loadings) and the glass fiber fabric layers. Large amount of energy is dissipated through a) the

stretching and breaking, spread through a large area around the impact zone, of the foamed matrix (Fig. 12) and b) larger deformations of fabrics (and in turn higher loads) permitted by the presence of pores in the matrix which allows a better accommodation of the reinforcing fibers before their failure.

Figure 12 Magnifications of stretched and broken foamed matrix after impact test at a distance of 20 mm from the impact point

Matrix Type	Peak Load (kN)	Absorbed Energy (J)
Neat Composite	5.65	39.0
EG Composite	6.09	43.2
Neat Foamed Comp.	6.05	56.4
EG Foamed Comp.	8.40	59.1
EG Sandwich	4.21	43.8

Table 4. Absorbed energy and peak loads for impacted composite structures

Figure 13. High energy impact responses

4 Conclusions

Glass fabric reinforced microcellular foams were prepared through the controlled generation of gas bubbles in a thermoplastic PEN matrix, thus

lowering the structure density from 1.65 to less than 1 g/cm³. The formation of a microcellular morphology in the composite matrix resulted in a slight reduction of the specific flexural modulus (lower than 20%) but in a strong enhancement of the specific impact properties (increased by 130%). The introduction of microcellular pores within the polymeric matrix and between reinforcing fibers, mimicked from natural composites, resulted in remarkable improvements of impact performances. Foamed composites showed residual elastic properties even at impact energies able to perforate the analogous conventional (solid) composite structure and beared higher impacts loads before failure, thus confirming the increased damage tolerance.

The developed lightweight fiber reinforced structure exhibited strongly improved impact resistance with respect to the conventional solid composite, showing that tailored voids in composite structures could be exploited as tougheners to strongly enhance the impact resistance. This result is due to the introduction of new dissipation mechanisms in the foamed matrix and to fibers which are allowed to bear higher tensile loads before breaking.

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